

Effect of Moonlight Tales on Social Cohesion among Middle Basic Pupils in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. The study adopted a non-randomized pretest posttest control group quasi-experimental research design. One research question and three hypotheses were raised. The population of the study consisted all pupils in middle basic schools in Osun State. The target population comprised of basic four pupils, sampled from four intact classes (2 private and 2 public schools), using simple random sampling technique. Social Cohesion Test (SCT) was developed to obtain valid information from the participants. Content validity was conducted by two experts in Childhood Education and Educational Psychology, while test re-test reliability used yielded index of 0.79. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research question, while the hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at a significant level of 0.05. The findings revealed that there was moderate level of social cohesion among pupils at the initial stage. Also, there was; significant effect of treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils, significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among the pupils, and significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. It was recommended that government should ensure the use of moonlight tales to bridge the gap between school and home cultural education, the use of moonlight tales is maintained by both private and public schools, the use of moonlight tales to enhance cultural inclusivity and social cohesion.

Keynotes: Moonlight tales, Folktales, Riddles, Social Cohesion, Moral values

Introduction

In a typical African Traditional setting, moonlight tales entail storytelling practice within the African culture, or an ethnic group in West Africa, particularly Nigeria. These tales are basically told in the evening or at night, often under the moonlight, creating a captivating and communal experience. The stories are passed down through generations and play a significant role in preserving and transmitting cultural values, history, and moral lessons. Moonlight tales are primarily an oral tradition. They are passed down verbally from one generation to another, relying on the spoken word to convey narratives. This reflects the rich oral culture of the people. The tales are not just for entertainment but serve as a means of educating and imparting cultural values. Through these stories, children and community members learn about their history, societal norms, and moral principles. Moonlight tales cover a wide range of themes, including folklore, mythology, morality, and historical events. These stories often feature animals, spirits, and mythical beings, providing explanations for natural phenomena and human experiences.

The values embedded in moonlight tales are diverse and reflect on the cultural, moral, and social principles of the people. Moonlight tales often emphasize the importance of moral integrity and ethical behaviour. Characters in the stories face moral dilemmas, and the resolution of these dilemmas provides lessons on the virtues of honesty, integrity, righteousness, etc. Many tales highlight the value of community cooperation and collective well-being. Characters work together to solve problems, reflecting the importance of unity and collaboration in Yoruba culture. Wisdom is highly valued in Yoruba culture, and many moonlight tales feature characters who demonstrate intelligence and the ability to solve problems through cleverness. These tales often emphasize the importance of acquiring knowledge and using it wisely (Ishola, 2015).

Moonlight tales are in two parts. One part precludes the other. There are *Àlò-àpamò* (riddles) and *Àlò-àpagbè* (folktales) (Akanni, 2014). *Àlò-àpamò* comes before *Àlò-àpagbè*. *Àlò-àpamò* is normally used to awaken and to arouse the interest of the listeners and make them ready for the story proper. It is also used to awaken and to arouse the intelligence of the audience. Olatunji (2014) stated five functions served by *Àlò-àpagbè*, which are; they help in keeping the audience mentally awake before folktales are told; they also serve as some entertainment value before the folktale is told, they exercise the intellect and wit of

the audience, they serve as instruction in social and material culture, they serve as an escape mechanism for the repressions brought about by the sanctions of the Yorùbá society.

Whatever moral value the story teller desires to pass across to his audience will form the basis of the story he chooses. There are different but significant moral and social values embedded in each story. For instance, there are lessons on hard work as against laziness, there are those on kindness and love as against wickedness and there are those on being hospitable as against being rude to the strangers and of course, there are those on contentment as against greediness and covetousness among many others. One other thing to be said before going into the narration of some of these stories is that some stories may be accompanied with singing in which the story teller leads and his audiences follow. When it is like this, the story teller is the one that gives the key points of the story in the song while the audience repeats the refrain or the chorus. The song is mostly intended to give aesthetic value to the story, to awaken the audience from their slumber (since the moonlight tales are told in the night after supper) and to also drive home the point the story teller is bringing to the fore (Akanni, 2014).

However, as numerous as the Yorùbá cultural concepts, the basic school curriculum has favoured some. Some parts of basic school Yoruba language curriculum teach about social cohesion among learners both young and adults. This provides an avenue through which life skills, principles, and values for personal, social, economic development are propagated (Cloete & Kotze, 2019). School safety and feelings of safety of both pupils and school personnel are expressed in issues, such as pupils' antisocial behaviour and violence in and around school, bullying, various disciplinary problems, and shooting incidents, all of which alert teachers, parents, and educational authorities (Bayh, 2015). In a reaction to this problem of social behaviour, the focus is directed at social cohesion or social climate characteristics of schools (Carbines, et al., 2016). National educational and local school policies concentrate on activities to assess or enhance school safety for both pupils and teachers (Cowie & Oztug, 2018). Moreover, increasing attention is being devoted to identifying correlates and possible causes of problem of social behaviour including the improvement of safety and feelings of safety at school

For safety and peaceful coexistence to be maintained, social cohesion has goal focusing on encouraging social change, and not only to transfer certain skills. It has to cover multiple segments of importance for peace building. Violence is not only direct and physical but can include the less obvious types of violence; structural (the one that is built into the system of governing themselves) and cultural (the aspects of culture that makes violence possible and acceptable), that create a fertile soil for the spreading of direct violence or more or less openly encourages it. One of the most things to measure are the sociological expressions that are aimed at behavioural change, especially when the students to be changed, and from whom the change in the school is expected, are living in an environment that is not changing, or it is changing to the worst. One of the elements that make behavior change difficult is culture (Cloete & Kotze, 2019). Thus, in order to establish durable peace in the school systems among the learners, administrators must analyze the structural causes of conflict and initiate social structural change. Therefore, social cohesion must be maintained to promote nonviolent mechanisms that eliminate violence, foster structures that meet basic needs, and maximise public participation (Cloete & Kotze, 2019).

Considering the foregoing, it will be observed that there are crucial lessons that could enhance the peaceful coexistence among learners within the school community. If the lessons are imbibed, the environment will be a harmonious place to live in. It is therefore imperative that moonlight tales should be put in the curriculum of both primary and secondary schools as a teaching strategy. Just as religious instructions are given to the students in schools for the purpose of inculcating the fear of God in them, so also, as moonlight tales are part of what the pupils have to be taught in schools, if properly used and maintained, it will go a long way in inculcating morals and morality in the learners. It is a known fact that all the immoral behaviours children are known within this present age are due to lack of moral discipline. If moonlight tales are put in the curriculum of schools, these will be used in instilling moral and cultural values in the children. There are lots of educational benefits derivable from moonlight tales, a traditional oral genre (Moser, 2017). This attests to the potency of the moonlight tales as an educational tool. With the current technological gadgets available for use in collection, documentation, dissemination and promotion of moonlight tales, today's children have abundant opportunity to access this oral genre.

Adeyemi (2017) attested to the assertion above where he stated that moonlight tales can be used to inculcate virtues in school age children such as humility, gratitude, respect for elders and constituted authority, perseverance, conformity to societal norms, co-operation, hospitality, truthfulness, honesty, willingness to take advice, patriotism, courage and love, loyalty to one's fatherland, hard work and the fear of God. Yorùbá culture is embedded with moral values, some of which are taught with the use of moonlight tales. If the young children are taught these moral values in schools, all the decadence we are witnessing today among the youth of our society will be minimized if not totally eradicated. This is why the study seek to find out the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

In the process of having modern civilization, knowledge about traditional culture and cultural heritage are being pushed aside or abandoned. This has created a great effect on the child's cultural knowledge, moral values, social behaviour

and this developed into its negative effects on the training of Yoruba children (Mercy, 2018). The moonlight tales not only has great advantage towards increasing pupils' cultural knowledge, but also influence their social cohesion, cultural attitudes, self-esteem, communication, and improves their personal entrepreneurial characteristics. Different writings have been about the benefits of moonlight tales, not only for children's entertainment but for their education and a fulfilling family life, some of which negates its effects on the social cohesion that exist among the school children. The rate of moral decadence in our society is becoming too high because parents have left their children in the hands of changing world and modern civilization in pursuit of material wealth. Thus, the traditional ways of inculcating virtues to children have been abandoned. This is as a result of the fact that parents, teachers and society at large have relented on the efforts to make use of the traditional means of training children through moonlight tales which could be in form of myths, folktales, folklores, and other forms of oral literature to instill moral values, societal norms, and virtues in the children.

Over the years, many studies have considered how moonlight tales are being told (Akanni 2014; Adeyemi, 2017; Mercy, 2018). These studies talked about the significance of folktales in moulding children's moral behaviour, how moonlight tales are being told, and the values embedded in it in reawaking the intelligent capability of the children. However, none of these studies identified moonlight tales as a strategy for moulding and shaping social behaviour among the children. This leaves a research gap which has to be filled to ensure relevant policy formulation on the use of moonlight tales in teaching pupils at basic level of education. Thus, the study seeks to investigate the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Objectives of the Study

The major purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic school pupils in Osun State. The study therefore sought to:

1. Examine the level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.
2. Investigate the significant effect of the treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.
3. Ascertain whether there is significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.
4. Ascertain whether there is significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Research Question

The following question was answered:

1. What is the level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant effect of the treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Methodology

The study focused on the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun state. It adopted a non-randomized pretest posttest control group quasi-experimental design. Pretest and posttest was administered to the experimental and control group. Pretest was administered in order to determine the equivalence of the two groups in their ability level. At the end of the treatment, posttest was also administered to the two groups to determine the significant difference if any, in the social cohesion among the pupils. Quasi-experimental design was considered appropriate for the study because intact classes were used to avoid disruption of normal class lessons. A pretest posttest control group quasi experimental design using 2x2x2 factorial design was used. The first two factorial levels were the experimental groups and the control group. The second factorial level was school ownership occurring in either private or public, while the third factorial level was the family type which occurs in either nuclear or extended family. This design allowed the experimental groups to receive treatment while control group did not receive. The control groups were exposed to the same pre-test with the experimental groups after which the experimental groups were subjected to the treatment. Both the experimental and control groups received the pre-tests and post-tests before and after the treatment respectively.

The population for the study consisted all pupils in middle basic schools in Osun State. The target population comprised of basic four Pupils in Osun Central Senatorial District. The sample consisted of basic four Pupils in four intact classes in the study area. The schools were selected using simple random sampling techniques. For this, four schools were randomly selected (Two Private and Two Public) and assigned control and experimental group using balloting. The researcher developed Social Cohesion Test (SCT) as research instrument to obtain valid information from the participants. These were made up of twenty (20) items drawn from the focusing areas. The instrument was in two sections. The first section which is section A consisted the demographic data (school ownership and family type) while section B consisted the test items on social cohesion.

The content validity of the instrument was done by two experts from Childhood Education and Educational Psychology, while test-retest reliability method was adopted by administering the test to 20 pupils different from the sample selected at two different time with interval of 2 weeks. The correlation between the response from the first and second administration was tested with the use of Pearson’s Product Movement Correlation (PPMC) which yielded an index of 0.79. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) for the research question raised, and inferential statistics (ANCOVA) was used to test the three hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significant.

Results

The data collected were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 23.0). The results of the findings are shown below:

Research Question

One research question was raised and was answered with the use of mean and standard deviation.

Research Question: What is the level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State?

In other to decide on the level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State, the total scores of each of the pupils (respondents) on the pretest given were summed up, having a total minimum of 2, maximum of 20 and the range of 18. This was categorized into three categorical form, which are Low, Moderate, and High. The three categories of low, moderate, and high were determined by dividing the range into three ($18 \div 3 = 6$). Hence, the interval scores between each category is 6. Therefore, the scores were arranged in the following categories to determine low, moderate, and high level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils: 2 – 7 is Low; 8 – 13 is Moderate; and 14 – 20 is High. The result is presented in the table below;

Table 1: Summary of the level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils

Level	Ranges	F	%	Remarks
Low	2 – 7	36	33.3%	
Moderate	8 – 13	49	45.4%	Moderate
High	14 – 20	23	21.3%	

Fieldwork, 2024

The above table revealed that 36 (33.3%) of the total pretest scores showed low level of social cohesion, 49 (45.4%) of the total pretest scores showed moderate level of social cohesion, while 23 (21.3%) of the total pretest scores showed high level of social cohesion. This revealed that majority (45.4%) of the scores from the pupils showed that social cohesion among middle basic pupils is on moderate level. This can therefore be concluded that there is moderate level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Hypotheses Testing

Three research hypotheses were formulated and tested with the use of Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA) at a significant level of 0.05.

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of the treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State

Table 2: Summary of (ANCOVA) showing significant effect of treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	243.78	2	121.89	7.88	.00	
Intercept	646.38	1	646.38	41.79	.00	
Pretest	29.78	1	29.78	1.93	.17	
Group	232.01	1	232.01	15.00	.00	*Sig.
Error	1624.22	105	15.47			
Total	2036.00	108				
Corrected Total	1868.00	107				

Fieldwork, 2024

Table 2 above showed the effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. It was revealed from the table above that there is significant effect of treatment on middle basic pupils' social cohesion. This was evident by significant value of 0.00 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis above which stated that there is no significant main effect of treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State is thereby rejected. Therefore, there is significant main effect of treatment on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

H₀₂: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Table 3: Summary of (ANCOVA) showing significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Intercept	747.98	1	747.98	32.66	.00	
Pretest	13.29	1	13.29	1.07	.30	
Group	220.18	1	220.18	2.00	.39	
School Ownership	241.29	1	241.29	2.37	.03	*Sig.
Group*School ownership	100.84	1	100.84	8.10	.01	*Sig.
Error	513.13	104	11.91			
Total	1850.00	108				
Corrected Total	1102.02	107				

Fieldwork, 2024

Table 3 above showed the interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in some selected schools in Osun State. It was revealed from the table above that school ownership does influence pupils' level of social cohesion. This was evident by significant value of 0.03 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Also, the sig value of 0.01 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05 indicated that both the treatment and school ownership have interaction effects on pupils' social cohesion. Hence, the null hypothesis above which stated that there is no significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State is rejected. Therefore, there is significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

H₀₃: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Table 4: Summary of (ANCOVA) showing significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Intercept	513.79	1	513.79	35.59	.00	
Pretest	50.11	1	50.11	3.31	.07	
Group	273.40	1	273.40	4.47	.28	
Family type	1.79	1	1.79	.03	.02	*Sig.

Group*Family type	60.87	1	60.87	4.02	.03	*Sig.
Error	515.27	104	12.23			
Total	1379.23	108				
Corrected Total	865.43	107				

Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 above showed the interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in some selected schools in Osun State. It was revealed from the table above that family type influence level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils. This was evident by significant value of 0.02 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Also, the sig value of 0.03 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05 indicated that both the treatment and family type have interaction effects on pupils' social cohesion. Hence, the null hypothesis above which stated that there is no significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State is rejected. Therefore, there is significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Discussions of the Findings

The study above revealed that there was moderate level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. This was seen from the pupils' scores on the pretest given before the treatment, where it was confirmed that middle basic pupils exhibit moderate social relationship as they show empathy, sympathy, love, care, affection, feelings to one and other both in and outside the classroom settings. This is as result of the fact that for peace and peaceful coexistence to maintained in school among teachers and the pupils, positive social behavior must be maintained, as this will pave ways for friendliness and peaceful coexistence. This was supported by the submission of Bayh (2015) who opined that school safety and feelings of safety of both pupils and school personnel are expressed in issues, such as pupils' antisocial behaviour and violence in and around school, bullying, various disciplinary problems, and shooting incidents, all of which alert teachers, parents, and educational authorities. In a reaction to this problem of social behaviour, the focus is directed to social cohesion or social climate characteristics of the schools. This was buttressed by Beauvais & Jenson (2012) who posited that, a school develops a rather specific social culture and ethos of its own, which is expressed also in a specific degree of social cohesion. In a school, each manager, teacher or staff member, or pupil perceives specific qualities of this social cohesion through specific feelings, beliefs, or behaviour of him or herself in relation to the other social actors, and vice.

Furthermore, it was revealed that there was significant effect of treatment (moonlight tales) on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. This was revealed by the significant value of the response 0.00 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. This is because pupils in experimental groups were exposure to the treatment package which tells them more about the significance value of social cohesion, gives them more knowledge about social cohesion and how it can be maintained to allow peaceful coexistence. This supported the assertion of Allport (2018), who reported that social cohesion reflects the degree of connectivity between the feelings, beliefs, actions, and behaviour tendencies of various social actors, which involve persons, social groups or categories, or institutions characterised by a multilevel organisation or framework. This was also spelt out of the educational policy at a national level which directed a variety of approaches, projects, and instruments to assess and improve school social cohesion and safety. Also, National Policy on Education, (NPE) clearly stated this to foster its effectiveness and as well included extra financial support for pedagogical and educational initiatives, for school boards to reduce or prevent violence, and for the monitoring of school safety and violent incidents in primary, secondary, and higher education (Mooij & De Wit, 2019).

Moreover, the findings showed that there was no significant interaction effect of treatment and school ownership on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. It was established from the findings that there was significant effect of treatment on pupils' social cohesion, as a result of the obtained sig value of 0.01 which is less than the Alpha value of .05. This revealed that both the treatment and school ownership have interaction on social cohesion among pupils. This is because there is difference in the level of social cohesion that exists among private school pupils and that of their counterparts from public schools. This was as a result of the fact the environment the pupils are exposed to and how conducive the environment determines the kind of relationship they share with each other. This goes in line with the submission of Mooij et al (2018), who submitted that a school develops a rather specific social culture and ethos of its own, which is expressed also in a specific degree of social cohesion. In a school, each manager, teacher or staff member, or pupil perceives specific qualities of this social cohesion through specific feelings, beliefs, or behaviour of him or herself in relation to the other social actors, and vice. The relative homogeneity in social culture and cohesion of a specific school, compared with that of other schools, is demonstrated in a series of nationwide survey studies.

Additionally, the findings revealed that there was significant interaction effect of treatment and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. This was revealed by the significant value of the response 0.03 which is less than the Alpha value of 0.05. This revealed that both the treatment and family type have interaction on pupils' social cohesion. This is because the social cohesion or relationship that exist among the pupils is affected by the type of family they come from. The social cohesion that pupils from nuclear family exhibit is different from their counterparts from the extended family. This is as a result of the fact the type of family the pupils come from, and as well as the kind of training given determines the kind of relationship they maintain with their peers. This corroborates the work of Flecha (2015), who opined that the typically close-knit nature of nuclear families allows for strong parent-child relationships and a solid foundation of social values. Parents in nuclear families often have the resources and time to engage in their children's social development, participating in activities that promote teamwork, empathy, and communication skills. These children may benefit from consistent parental involvement and guidance, which helps them navigate social situations effectively and build strong peer relationships. But in extended families, children often grow up surrounded by a variety of role models and support systems, which can enhance their social competence and adaptability. The presence of multiple generations and a larger family circle in extended families means that children are exposed to diverse perspectives and social dynamics from an early age.

Conclusion

From the forgoing, it was concluded that there was moderate level of social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State at the initial stage of the experiment. After the administration of the treatment, there was significant effect of moonlight tales on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State. It was revealed from the study that there was significant interaction effect of moonlight tales and school ownership on social cohesion among the pupils, and there was significant interaction effect of moonlight tales and family type on social cohesion among middle basic pupils in Osun State.

Recommendations

- The following recommendations are proffer so as to establish the significance of moonlight tales
1. Government should ensure the integration of moonlight tales into the formal school curriculum as part of language arts, social studies, or cultural education classes, as this will promote social cohesion among the pupils.
 2. School management should ensure the involvement of families and community members in the use of moonlight tales to bridge the gap between school and home cultural education.
 3. Government should ensure the use of moonlight tales to foster cultural knowledge and social cohesion among pupils is be maintained by both private and public schools.
 4. School management should ensure the development and implementation of policies that promote the use of moonlight tales so as to enhance cultural inclusivity and social cohesion.

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